

**CASE COMMENT: BHIKAJI NARAIN DHAKRAS & ORS. VS. THE
STATE OF MADHYA PRADESH & ORS. 1955 AIR 781**

by

Anirudh Thakur

ICFAI Law School, Dehradun

EQUIVALENT CITATIONS: 1955 SCR (2) 589

PETITIONER:

Bhikaji Narain Dhakras and Ors.

RESPONDENT:

The State of Madhya Pradesh and Ors.

DATE OF JUDGEMENT:

28th September 1955

BENCH:

Sudhi Ranjan Das, Acting C.J.; H. Bhagwati; L.Venkatarama Aiyar; Syed Jaffer Imam;
Chandresekhar Aiyar, JJ.

CASES CITED IN THIS CASE ANALYSIS:

1. Shagir Ahmad v. The State of U.P. & Others, [1955] 1 SCR 70
2. Keshavan Madhava Menon v. The State of Bombay, 1951 Cri LJ 680

3. Deep Chand v. State of Uttar Pradesh and Ors., AIR 1959 SC 648
4. Keshavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala and Anr., (1973) 4 SCC 225

BACKGROUND: -

The C.P and Berar Motor Vehicles (Amendment) Act, 1947 (Act III of 1948) which stated that the state government can exclude any private vehicles from the transportation business was challenged by the petitioners as according to them the said act was violative of the Article 19 (1)(g) which provided the right to every citizen of India to Practice any occupation or carry on any business. The above-mentioned case helped the Indian Judiciary in order to Interpret the existing laws with the newly framed Constitution. The courts also introduced the Doctrine of Eclipse. The abovementioned act was implemented before the constitution by the amendment of the Motor Vehicles Act, 1939. The main objective of this act was to increase the control of the British Officers over the transportation of goods. The act also allowed the state government to fix the prices for the various carriers either public, contract, stage which could also lead to increase in competition. This petition by the petitioners miserably failed as before this case was filed the Fourth Constitutional Amendment, 1954 which added the 19(6)(i) which stated that the State government can prevent practice of any occupation or carrying on of any business on the ground of technical or practical qualification. Thus, the court held the act in question to be valid.

FACTS: -

C.P Transport Services and Provincial Transport Company Ltd. are companies situated in Madhya Pradesh and are the major private transport companies in the region and the Union holding over 85% of the share capital in the market which gives the government the sole power to influence the transport Business of the private sector. Five Writ petitions were filed under Art. 32 of the Indian Constitution. The Petitioners have filed the petitions as before the C.P and Berar Act, 1947 the Petitioners were granted permit to carry on their carriage operations under the Motor Vehicles Act, 1939. And the implementation of the C.P and Berar Act would affect the fundamental right of a

number of citizens who work under the transport business and will also give enormous powers to State to regulate the business.

ISSUES RAISED BEFORE THE COURT: -

1. Whether the act which Amended the Motor Vehicles Act, 1939 i.e., the C.P and Berar Amendment Act, 1947 constitutionally valid?
2. Whether the Act violates the Article 19 (1)(g) of the Constitution?
3. Whether the act is violative of Art 31?
4. Whether judicial review provided under Article 13 is allowed of the laws which existed before the Constitution?
5. Whether Monopoly and Prohibition by State come under the reasonable restriction provided under Article 19(6)?
6. Whether the effects of the Constitutional Amendments are Retrospective or Prospective?

PETITIONER'S CONTENTION: -

1. The Petitioner Contended that the C.P and Berar Motor Vehicles Amendment Act is violative of Article 19(1)(f) of the Indian Constitution and it should be declared invalid.
2. The Petitioners Contended that the Act is void as it is unconstitutional.
3. The Petitioners contended that The Act became void as soon as the Constitution came into force and cannot be revived by any subsequent Amendment.
4. The Petitioners contended that the Act violates the right of a citizen to property as it prohibits the person to induct their vehicles in the transport business and is thus violating Article 31.
5. The Petitioners contended that the 1st and the 4th Amendment are not retrospective in nature and thus the Act cannot be revived.

6. Petitioners have relied upon Cooley's work on Constitutional Limitation, Vol. I, p. 384 Note and Shagir Ahmed v. State of Uttar Pradesh and Ors. (1955) 1 SCR 707.
7. That the Act should be declared unconstitutional as it violates Part III of the Constitution.

RESPONDENT'S CONTENTION: -

1. The Respondents contended that the First Constitutional Amendment Act, 1951 removed the inconsistency of the Act.
2. That the Fundamental rights provided to the Citizens of India under article 19 are subject to certain limitations provided under clause 2-6 of the same Article.
3. That the 1st Constitutional Amendment Act made amendments to Article 19(6) which imposed restrictions on the Fundamental rights to practicing any occupation, trade, business, profession.
4. That the Act is not violating the fundamental rights as the law was made in by taking the general interest of the public in mind and that the law also enables the state to become a monopoly so it can work for the benefit of its citizens.
5. That as the Act is not violating any of the Fundamental rights hence it is not violative of the Constitution thus the petition should be dismissed.

JUDGEMENT: -

RATIO DECIDENDI: The court in the case Keshavan Madhava Menon v. The State of Bombay, stated that a law does not become completely void but only that part of the law becomes void which is inconsistent with the Part III of the Constitution. The court also stated that the law which became inconsistent with the constitution after being declared as void governs the past transactions and enforces the rights and liabilities which arose when the law was in force even against the noncitizens.

The court Stated for the present case that if the amendment of the constitution was not made the act in question would have been declared void as it interferes with the right of a person to practice

any business, carry on any trade. But as the Constitution was amended in 1951 and the First Constitutional amendment came into force the defect of the act in question was removed which was the maintaining of monopoly by the state in transport/carriage business.

Court observed that Article 19(6) was not retrospective in nature therefore, it cannot be applied for the rights and liabilities that arose between 26th January, 1950 and 18th June 1955 but after the amendment the restrictions are applicable to all the citizens.

Coming on to the contention that the fundamental right to property has been affected by the act. As per the Court the Fourth Constitutional Amendment Act, 1955 saved the act in question by amending Article 31. The court also stated that the petition was filed on 27th May 1955 while the defect of the act was itself cleared on 27th April 1955.

OBITER DICTA: The court stated that if the petitioners had filed their petitions before 27th April 1955 that is before the First Constitutional Amendment Act came into force then their pleas would have been considered as the Constitutional Amendments do not have retrospective effects. Similar cases have been dealt by the Judiciary i.e., before and after amendment. The court also stated that the claim of the petitioners that their fundamental right of property is being affected is also being affected by the act in question cannot be considered as this point was taken during the course of the arguments. The petitioners counted on the American Authorities to a great extent whereas India had to deal with both pre and post constitutional laws.

ANALYSIS: -

Comparing the past to the present it is quite visible that there has been a huge shift in the power that has been granted to the parliament. The courts observed that the constitutional amendments which were passed were in order to authorize the laws passed before the commencement of the constitution. It was also observed that the Fundamental Rights provided by the constitution are the only tests which can determine the validity of the Act but there was no concern on the power of the government to amend the constitution and create laws.

The petitioners filed the present case while viewing a similar case Shagir Ahmed case in which the UP Act which is similar to C.P Berar Act, 1947. But the case was filed before the Amendments whereas, in the present case the case was filed way after the Amendments were made. The court stated that the word restriction can be interpreted as limitation and if the state achieves monopoly in the road transport, then it is against the freedom of profession. The amendments in constitution allowed the governments to gain monopoly in a particular field for the interest of general public and reasonable restrictions.

The Petitioners in this case failed not because of any political interference but because of their own delay. The Writ petitions should be filed within reasonable time so that a perfect cause of action can be derived. Even though the Constitutional Amendments were not retrospective the delay by the petitioners upheld the constitutionality of the Act.

Indian Journal of Contemporary
Legal and Social Issues